

FAIR DIGITAL OBJECTS FORUM

FDO Bulletin 2022-2 June 2022

Participate in Commenting FDOF Recommendations
(see below)
Submit Abstracts for the FDO Conference until 10.7
(see below)

1st FDO Conference 26-28. October and Call for Abstracts

From 26 to 28. October 2022 we will organise the first FDO Conference in Leiden in the realm of the activities of Leiden as city of Science in 2022. We also published the [Call for Abstracts with 10.7 as deadline](#). All information about the conference and the CfA you can find here: <https://www.fdo2022.org/> Reserve the conference in your agenda, inform your colleagues about this event and motivate them to participate.

For the two keynotes on data science and technology we will engage distinguished experts from the research and technology domains and will soon be ready to announce them.

Request for Comments on FDOF Recommendations

The following documents are now ready for open commenting by the FDO Community, i.e. all experts registered via the fairdo.org website. All these documents have undergone extensive discussions within the FDO Forum and can now be commented on by interested FDO Community members until **30.7.2022**. We see this as a major step ahead.

PED-DOIPEndorsement-1.0-20220608	2022-07-30	https://docs.google.com/document/d/10ESWe-m0ex7fiW0ZY0YeVg6gAclABKyO3W-Vg8tXzdw/edit?usp=sharing
PEN-FDO-Upload-1.0-20220608	2022-07-30	https://docs.google.com/document/d/1Qi1YHzoyaetDjngBUkZBFl-iaUjHh9UE1mgKXPfGiDy8/edit?usp=sharing
PR-TypingFDOs-2.0-20220608	2022-07-30	https://docs.google.com/document/d/1N94nw81DfT383_dDcfZeu_5QCRQYpq_f8iaVQdNxFmE/edit?usp=sharing
PR-Granularity-2.0-20220608	2022-07-30	https://docs.google.com/document/d/1FKenu_ZwJPukMFsf9z_ligAHBqw98EFnC2v6LUsW_ts/edit?usp=sharing
PR-PIDProfileAttributes-2.0-20220608	2022-07-30	https://docs.google.com/document/d/16zxfnC47vZM4q-dyJoi9XsQMqqHnp11Ajvr55F6y6Ww/edit?usp=sharing
PR-ConfigurationTypes-2.0-20220608	2022-07-30	https://docs.google.com/document/d/1N94nw81DfT383_dDcfZeu_5QCRQYpq_f8iaVQdNxFmE/edit?usp=sharing
PR-MachineActionDef-2.0-20220611	2022-07-30	https://docs.google.com/document/d/15hoyiaYf8t5tZrQdKb738lg2_spEZCNU-nIKq8lWu10Y/edit?usp=sharing

We should note that there are two more documents still being discussed within the FDOF:

- A detailed description of the FDO Typing System which will be one of the core documents
- A discussion of mandatory Kernel Attributes

The FDO community is approaching 400 members and we need to see how commenting will proceed.

Community Interaction Meeting

The third Community Interaction Meeting will be devoted to present and discuss the FDO documents as they now have been put out for comments. There may be many questions about the documents where the responsible people should give answers.

The Community Interaction Meeting will be on 13. July 2022 at 15.00 focussing on Q/A about the proposed FDOF recommendations.

FDO Forum Activities

The FDO Forum is strengthening its organisational form slightly after its Steering Committee has been extended to cover all major regions of the world which also required to have alternating meetings to allow participation of everyone. This and the extended workload on the co-chairs required to form an efficiently working Executive Committee. This idea is currently being discussed.

The SC decided to start working on short videos to introduce FDO topics in a way so that it is easy for newcomers to understand the concepts behind FDOs and see what is available and what needs to be developed.

The FDO Foudm is inviting its new members to present their work. Washington Segundo and Mikiko Tanifuji gave already excellent presentations about data related work in Brazil and Japan.

FDOF also decided to strengthen the communication and interaction based on a communication plan. The first concrete results are to organise FDOF Lectures (first on 16.6) and to create short video clips with explanations about major FDO aspects. We hope to use the summer break to create first ones.

The collaboration with the German DIN(ISO) led to a number of interactions and meetings with industry and government experts in Germany.

16. June	17.30 CEST (15.30 UTC)	FDOF Lecture	Robert Hanisch (NIST)	International Work on Units
24. June	16.00 CEST (14.00 UTC)	CWFR Meeting	Ilkay Altintas (SDSC)	US Workflow Report
21. July	18.30 CEST (16.30 UTC)	FDOF Lecture	Stefan Weisgerber (DIN/ISO)	Standardisation and Perspectives for FDOF-DIN/ISO collaboration

Name the Thing Initiative

We know that there will be a globally integrated domain of data (and perhaps services), but we still do not have a convincing NAME for this. Convincing names are like "Internet", "Web" or "FAIR" for example since they are easy to remember and give an immediate semantic bridge to the topic. We would like to open a broad discussion about a suitable name and would like to motivate the FDO Community to make suggestions. We hope that at least at our October conference we can agree on a convincing name which is not already used for other purposes such as "datanet".

So please have a look at the suggestions which have already been made and add your own suggestions. The link to the web template is here: <https://fairdo.org/fdo-forum-contest-name-that-space/>

FDOF - Industry Interaction

Due to the collaboration with DIN many interactions with industry took place which is highly engaged in projects such as Industry 4.0, Big Data Value Association, GAIA-X, OPC UA etc. All these initiatives are meant to improve the efficiency in industrial processes and when working with data. FDO Forum was invited again to present the FDO concept with leading persons from industry and two concrete actions were agreed upon: (1) Industry worked on the Industry 4.0 Administration Layer and it was agreed to look into how FDOs could interact with this layer. (2) Industry and politics are discussing the Digital Product Pass which for example is meant to contain all contributions of green house gas emissions during the whole life cycle. Here we ware looking how FDOs could be used to implement such a process. It seems that we can start some joint activities and further detailed meetings are scheduled. Important for us was that a few leading industry people clearly expressed that we need to join forces to come to a widely agreed standard.

Institutional Support

We decided to ask institutions and organisations to support the FDOF work. No money and obligations are being asked, but we would like to demonstrate that relevant institutions support our work and give backing to their employees to spend some time on FDO work.

So we are asking all FD Community members to seek support by filling in the corresponding web-form: <https://fairdo.org/organizational-membership/>

Working Groups

Joint Work on Typing

The joint work on typing ended with finalising one general document on the FDO Typing System. TSIG and BIG WGs are now working on a detailed and comprehensive plan about FDO Typing. This document is currently in the phase where all FDO WG are requested to give comments. When all substantial comments have been resolved, this document will also be presented to the FDO community.

TSIG (Technical Specification & Implementation Group)

TSIG work was focussing on finalising the FDO documents to become Proposed Recommendations and discussed the missing documents about Mandatory Kernel Attributes and the FDO Typing System in detail. In addition, the intention is to write a Full FDO Specification document which includes the essentials from all FDO documents and which should become ready before the October conference.

Inspired by industry discussions the TSIG group also started discussions about FDO Content Negotiation and what an advanced FDO Machine could look be. An attempt to discuss interoperability aspects with the Signposting colleagues did not turn out, since according to the colleagues there is nothing to be discussed.

BIG (Basic Infrastructure Group)

BIG played a major role in finalizing the working draft on FDO typing and now started a new working draft on the Implementation of Attributes, Types, Profiles and Registries that explains the relationships between FDO components on a conceptual level and describes the resulting constrains for implementing them. Furthermore, the BIG group is currently setting up a testbed infrastructure for running crucial FDO services on demand.

SEM (Semantic Group)

FDO-SEM is currently working on applying the FDOF model (proposed by Luiz Bonino) to a real-world research use case during a series of hackathons. The use case is taken from the NFDI4DataScience consortium of the German National Research Data Infrastructure (NFDI) initiative and addresses a skin lesion analysis dataset from the health domain. The group presented results of its work to the NFDI community in the framework of the NFDI InfraTalk series on June 20th. The next step will be to write a paper on the FDOF application to the health use case

CWFR (Canonical Workflows for Research)

The CWFR group made a plan for the next two meetings in the first half of 2022. The first talk was about industry interoperability standards (eCLASS, OPC UA) and the next talk will be on 24.6 about the comprehensive analysis about the state of WFs in the US research. We will announce a topic for September early enough and then participate in the October conference. We would like to motivate all interesting people to submit an abstract (see above).

Responsible for this FDO Bulletin are the FDO-SC Co-Chairs:
Christine Kirkpatrick, Dimitris Koureas, George Strawn, Peter Wittenburg
Comments/question can be sent to secretariat@fairdo.org

